

THE EFFECT OF ORGANIZATIONAL LEARNING ON UNIVERSITIES PERFORMANCE “EMPIRICAL STUDY ON THE UNIVERSITIES IN JORDAN”

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Abstract

This study has investigated the influences of the effect of organizational learning on universities performance “Empirical Study on the Universities in Jordan”. The study used, a quantitative approach was employed to collect data, where this was applied by distributing a questionnaire. The results show that organizational learning (Individual learning, Group learning) has a significant impact on universities performance on the Universities in Jordan”. Results of this study offer several implications for researchers and Universities in Jordan. For researchers, it enriches the research on the relationship organizational learning and universities performance. Some limitations to this study should be noted, and efforts to resolve them would serve as avenues for future research in this field. First, the findings of the study may have limited generalizability. The sample, which seemed appropriate for this particular study.

INTRODUCTION:

Globalization has resulted in drastic changes in the environment, competition, and dynamic customer preferences, and this has forced organizations to adapt themselves to these issues in order to survive and succeed. These changes have occurred not only in the external environment, such as in products, services, and technologies, but also in the internal environment, like the way people think, their visions, values, and goals (Seyed and Khazaei, 2014). In order to be empowered to deal with these changes, organizations should focus on organizational learning. In fact, a successful organization learns faster and adapts more quickly than its competitors. This is why attention to concepts of organizational learning has grown and been emphasized more strongly in recent years (Khanalizadeh, et al., 2010).

Organizational learning has increasingly attracted attention in organizations that focus on increasing competitive advantages, innovation, and effectiveness. Organizational learning is a process that leads to employees' learning, and it includes specific organizational behavior observed in the learning organizations. Have described organizational learning as a way of

consolidating and stabilizing the organization, completing and organizing current knowledge about organizational activities and culture, as well as improving the process of activities through better knowledge and understanding. Because of its importance, this concept has been classified from different views. One of the most well-known and comprehensive ones is Neefe's perspective in which organizational learning consists of seven dimensions, including shared vision, organizational culture, team learning, system thinking, participative leadership, personal mastery and sharing knowledge. Paying attention to organizational learning, particularly in higher education systems, is one of the most important aspects of sustainable development (Albrecht et al, 2015).

This is because universities are the most important elements of the teaching-learning process in society today (Davodi and Oshtori, 2011). Therefore, organizational learning is the main way to make knowledge work and improve organizational efficiency, particularly in the education system. Achieving organizational learning requires careful and constant attention to the empowerment of human resources at all organizational levels. Employees are the most important asset of an organization; hence, empowering them and creating motivated and empowered staff will allow managers to act quickly and appropriately in a changing and dynamic environment and provide competitive advantages for their organizations (Allahyari, et al., 2011).

Organizational empowerment means to empower employees; in other words, to help them to strengthen their self-confidence, overcome their sense of powerlessness and helplessness, and motivate them to perform activities. In empowerment, the employees will be given greater autonomy, self-determination, freedom and responsibility for making decisions. In fact, this concept can be seen as a set of motivational techniques that seek to increase the level of employees' participation in order to improve their performance (Bates, R. and Khasawneh, S. (2015). Universities, like any other organization, are working in a variable and dynamic environment. In order to empower these organizations to deal with constant change, they should focus on organizational learning.

BACKGROUND STUDY:

With the beginning of the new millennium, universities sought to search about the latest management systems, in order to ensure the transition to a knowledge-based society which depending in its economy on producing knowledge instead of capital or labor force. Communities began reviewing their educational systems administration, to improve their learning outcomes (Bolarinwa, 2019). Since the university which will success in the future is the one which can discover how to benefit from the learning capabilities of all its members The establishment of specialized universities in organizational learning field has supported this trend, as (SOL) The International Society for Organizational Learning (Bontis et al. 2002).

The twenty-first century witnessed a global competition in the university learning environment because of progress in technique and knowledge. Where the higher education systems became exposed to job stresses which made universities administrations concerned about applying the recent trends: such as organizational learning concept to keep up with global changes (Goh,

2019). Universities are one of the most influential organizations in the community; their success depends on their ability to face the rapid changes, emphasize that universities should change their administrative systems, and obtain the concepts of the organizational learning; for development and performance improvement. Where (Hongand Mak2019). Shows that applying the concept of organizational learning to universities is through continuous learning, through abandonment of traditional management practices, and adopting models and modern administrative approaches.

Defined that learning as the process in which knowledge is created through experience. Learning is a relatively permanent change in behavior that occurs because of a person's interaction with an environment (Kaminska and Borzillo, 2018).

According to (Senaratne and Malewana, 2011) stated that if organizations have a good learning culture, people are encouraged to improve individual learning through collective learning. Therefore, the relationship between learning culture and performance in an organization has gained interest in different disciplines. Overall performance is difficult to measure and diagnose in an organization. Researchers have proposed various approaches for measuring organizational performance.

Organizational learning as a vital constituent strategic management and performance evaluation based on its influence on process improvement and innovation. a number of definitions are presented by different scholars some of which are as follows:

Organizational learning (OL): is the development of new knowledge or insights that have the potential to influence behavior. Organizational learning is defined as the capacity or processes within an organization to maintain or improve performance based on experience. Organizational learning is the intentional use of learning processes at the individual, group and system levels to continuously transform the organization in a direction that is increasingly satisfying to its stakeholders.

Organizational learning is the creating, acquiring and transferring of distinctions and practices in the organization. Organizational learning is the ability of an organization to gain insight and understanding from experience, Organizational learning means the process of improving actions through better knowledge and understanding, organizational learning is a process of detecting and correcting errors (Kyoungshin and Zhenqiu2019).

Universities Performance (UP): In English, the term "performance" is derived from "to perform" which means "doing work, achieving a mission or realizing a given activity. It is a reflection of the organization's ability and aptitude to realize its goals. It is the ability of the university to achieve its long-term goals. UP is that which exceeds the normal average performance, besides being a part of a series of excellent performance Universities that attempt to realize UP have their own characteristics that turn them different from conventional performance. The university's performance reflects that of its employees. (Marquardt, M.J. (2019) has presented a number of features for organizations of UP. They are as follows Organizational learning as an approach to achieve outstanding performance.

Problem Statement:

With the new definition of organization as a “body of thought,” Organizational Learning (OI) has become as an important and interesting. Mental powers become the powers that govern in new organizations Reese, S. (2020), Thus, organizations are shifting nowadays to improve their mental and physical abilities which would in turn affect and activate the organization different activities; to achieve the organization success, shape its knowledge, achieve its missions and goals, as well as influence the organization effectiveness, efficiency, productivity and performance and measure its fitness and empower it to be able to solve its problems (Ortenblad, 2019). Organizational Learning refers to the cognitive, discursive, and material process through which an organization and its members aim to expand their existing capabilities.

According to (Retna and Jones2013)) organizational learning is the practices and tools the organization provides its people individually and collectively for them to perform their work successfully and efficiently. Organizational learning occurs through history based learning. History based learning consists of allowing outcomes of past. Organizational behavior to guide future organizational choices. This requires actors within the organization to embed certain organizational routines in an organization often through recording them in organizational rulebooks or through stories that get passed down orally. History based learning involves constantly analyzing the outcomes of past organizational behavior to determine whether these outcomes are beneficial enough to continue in future organizational action (Saadat and Saadat, 2016)). This type of learning is often vulnerable to information getting lost as a result of leadership transitions or the inability to properly record organizational memories. In addition, organizations are sensitive to competency traps, the idea that organizations become adept in certain. Processes and are blinded to potentially more efficient processes.

The process of organizational learning is complex and comprised of many organizational sub-processes. The literature suggests four key processes are crucial to organizational learning: resource acquisition strategies, governance structures, leadership succession systems, and organizational routines (Hong and Mak, 2019).

Appreciate that organizational learning is necessary for the survival of a business. We appreciate that this is true not only in the case of profit-based organizations, but also in the case of higher education institutions. We appreciate that the academic environment can develop and can reach better performances and master sustainable competitive advantages primarily by changing from the inside, not at the request coming from the outside. For universities, in particular, learning is part of the daily activities, but, they might be faced with a paradox: “although a university is an organization based on learning processes, it is not necessarily a learning organization” in any organization: there are two types of processes the production process and the management process. In the case of universities, the production process is a learning process, but, in order for a university to be a learning organization, the management process needs to be a learning process too. Learning organizations are considered, organizations where people continually expand their capacity to create the results they truly desire, where new and expansive patterns of thinking are nurtured, where collective aspiration is set free, and where people are continually learning how to learn together”. States that

universities have the possibility to become learning organizations “if and only if there is at least a strong integrator to assure the transition from individual learning to team and organizational learning”.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES:

1. Statement effect of organizational learning on the universities performance of the faculty members in the public and private Jordanian universities.
2. Statement effect of individual learning on the universities performance of the faculty members in the public and private Jordanian universities.
3. Statement effect of group learning on the universities performance of the faculty members in the public and private Jordanian universities.

Significance of study:

The importance of research justified in the following points:

1. The lack of studies and research that Dealing with the impact of organizational learning on universities performance in universities to the knowledge of the researcher.
2. Addressing a subject that has a reflection on the performance of the universities in the Jordanian universities and thus the overall performance of the universities.
3. Drew the attention of the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research in Jordan to the need of encouraging universities to adopt organizational learning culture.
4. Finding recommendations and proposals that enhance the levels of organizational learning in public and private Jordanian universities.

Research Design

This research is regarded as a descriptive and analytical research, since it aims to describe the variables under study with no intervention. The goal of descriptive research is to describe a phenomenon and its characteristics. In this study, a quantitative approach was employed to collect data, where this was applied by distributing a questionnaire. (Sukamolson, 2007).

Population and Sample

To increase generalizability, it is important to choose the sample that represented the population under investigation. The target population of the study is all of the faculty members in public and private Jordanian universities. A Convenience sample of 700 of the faculty members of the population size. After distributing (700) questionnaires of the study sample, a total of (650) completely answered questionnaires were retrieved.

Reliability of the instrument

Table (1) displays reliability test results. Cronbach's alpha is a test of internal consistency for the instrument. The table illustrated that overall Cranach's alpha coefficient score for the

instrument of the study was good (0.90), however, they are acceptable scores according to some citations (Peterson, 1994).

Descriptive analysis for the scales

Table (1) shows the dimension's analysis of the study. Based on the findings, the overall score (3.95). In specific, all items were perceived as good. Accordingly, the descriptive statistics concerning the dimensions (organizational learning, universities performance) is considered to be good in terms of level from the perspective of the study's sample.

Table 1: Descriptive analysis for the dimensions of the study

Item #	The dimensions	X	STD	Level
1	Individual learning.	4.00	0.82	Good
2	Group learning	3.98	0.79	Good
3	The universities performance	3.89	0.84	Good
	Total	3.95	0.82	Good

Results of testing the study's hypotheses:

Through this part, the researcher of the present study presents the results of testing the main hypothesis. The main hypothesis was tested through carrying out the multiple linear regression analysis. The results of this analysis are shown in table 9 below.

Table 2: The results of the multiple linear regression analysis for testing the main hypothesis

Hypotes	Model Summary			ANOVA			Coefficient					
	R	R ²	Adj R ²	F	F.Sig	DF	Dimension	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig
H ₀	0.675	0.456	0.452	81.107	0.00	291/3	Individual learning	0.141	0.045	0.176	3.109	0.002
							Group learning	0.091	0.045	0.099	2.032	0.043

H0.1: organizational learning (Individual learning, Group learning) doesn't have any significant impact at the statistical significance level of ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) - on universities performance Empirical Study on the Universities in Jordan.

Based on table (2), organizational learning (Individual learning, Group learning) has a significant impact on universities performance on the Universities in Jordan". That is because the sign value is 0.00 which is less than 0.05. It is because the calculated F value is 81.107 which is greater than the tabulated F value (2.60). The R value is 67.5%. That indicates that there is a strong relationship between organizational learning and universities performance R² is 0.456. That indicates that 45.6% of the changes that universities performance are attributed to organizational learning.

Discussion

The objective of this study was to examine the effect of organizational learning on universities performance “Empirical Study on the Universities in Jordan”. This study concludes that organizational learning has positive impact on universities performance that is consistent with findings of Bolarinwa, 2019; Bontis et al. 2002 and Goh, 201, Hong and Mak2019. Show that organizational learning positively affects universities performance “Empirical Study on the Universities in Jordan”.

Since organizational learning is a central concern to all Universities and firms, so organizations should encourage to share work experiences or learning reflections, and universities should actively explore the current market and related information and actively improve their professional competencies and should set work-related goals and try to accomplish them to enhance organizational performance directly and indirectly through organizational performance because the creation of innovative culture through learning allows firm to achieve a better competitive position and above-average performance.

Results of this study offer several implications for researchers and Universities in Jordan. For researchers, it enriches the research on the relationship organizational learning and universities performance. Some limitations to this study should be noted, and efforts to resolve them would serve as avenues for future research in this field. First, the findings of the study may have limited generalizability. The sample, which seemed appropriate for this particular study.

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